

Review

Toward all flexible sensing systems for next-generation wearables

Fengyuan Liu^{a,b,*}, Leandro Lorenzelli^{a,**}^a *Microsystems Technology (MST) Research Unit, Center for Sensors & Devices, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento 38123, Italy*^b *Bendable Electronics and Sustainable Technologies (BEST) Group, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Northeastern University, Boston, MA 02115, USA*

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Flexible and printed electronics
 Flexible integrated circuits
 Analog front-end
 Internet-of-things
 Edge computing

ABSTRACT

Recent advances in science and technology have enabled a promising future for wearable devices with the ability to seamlessly interact with their users. The next generation of wearable systems should be fully flexible, conformable, multifunctional, and energy autonomous. Over the past decade or two, significant progress has been made in wearable soft sensors, whereas the development of flexible integrated circuits (ICs) for sensing front-end and data processing is just starting to gain momentum. This review article comprehensively examines the state of the art in flexible ICs for wearable applications. It discusses the progress and challenges in various dimensions, including materials, devices, and circuits. The paper further discusses essential algorithms for processing sensor data and provides insights into their hardware implementations. A co-design strategy is emphasized to holistically address the realization of wearable systems at different levels. By shedding light on the ongoing progress and challenges in the field, this paper provides a forward-looking perspective for future efforts in advancing flexible sensing systems for the next generation of wearables and aims to attract a wider readership in relevant fields.

1. Introduction

Today, we are on the brink of unprecedented connectivity with the outside world, the Internet of Everything [1,2]. This requires the development, deployment, and distribution of a very large number of sensors to facilitate the extraction and interpretation of information and thereby aid in the planning and execution of actions [3,4]. Smart wearables have emerged as a key catalyst, attracting considerable attention for their potential to enable intimate, convenient, and unceasing human-machine interaction, to continuously collect the most delicate and private physiological data, and to provide users with up-to-date health and fitness information [5–8]. Such a capability allows the users to make more informed decisions to guide their real-life actions. Consider a hypothetical scenario such as a football training session: the integration of smart vests worn by players could facilitate continuous monitoring and analysis of their physiological indicators without impeding their movement during the game. Real-time access to valuable data opens avenues for interpreting each individual's physical and emotional state, enabling the coaching team to conduct detailed analyses of performance and fitness. This, in turn, allows for the development of personalized training plans tailored to each player. Such a

real-time context awareness, interpretation and response are made possible only by the integration of wearable physical and bio-sensors capable of detecting crucial physiological indicators such as heart rate and adrenaline, a machine learning algorithm that classifies the user's status based on the data fed-in, and a communication module that transmits the results.

The history of wearables can be traced back to the mid to late 20th century, exemplified by the conceptual prototype demonstration of the fitness trackers and wearable PCs, the latter of which was first developed by Thorp and Shannon to provide profitable gambling strategies in casinos (e.g., to predict roulette wheels) without arousing the suspicions from the dealer and other gamblers [9,10]. However, these early demonstrations lacked true flexibility and posed constraints. Most were characterized by the rigid and bulky system that users could carry only with the help of flexible fixings/wirings, highlighting the room for improvements in user experience. Today, thanks to research progress in disciplines such as material science, electronics, chemistry, biomedical engineering, and more, innovations in smart wearables have been noteworthy: Various electronic components, including sensors, logic devices, displays, energy devices, have been successfully integrated onto soft wearable substrates (e.g., yarn and textiles) [11–17], showcasing a

Peer review under the responsibility of Editorial Board of Wearable Electronics.

* Corresponding author at: Microsystems Technology (MST) Research Unit, Center for Sensors & Devices, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Trento 38123, Italy.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: fliu@fbk.eu, fe.liu@northeastern.edu (F. Liu), lorenzeli@fbk.eu (L. Lorenzelli).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wees.2024.07.003>

Received 5 April 2024; Received in revised form 1 July 2024; Accepted 9 July 2024

Available online 22 August 2024

2950-2357/© 2024 The Authors. Publishing services by Elsevier B.V. on behalf of KeAi Communications Co. Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

promising future where wearables not only enhance their comfortableness but hold the capability to redefine our way of interacting with the external world. Apart from the integration aspect, the development of flexible sensors itself is worth mentioning: Presently, we are nowhere far away from creating sensors with excellent performance such as high sensitivity, high specificity, high linearity, low hysteresis, miniaturized size, lightweight design, mechanical compliance, and resilience to daily wear and tear, capable of detecting changes in force, temperature, strain, chemical and biological species [18–24]. These sensors have evolved from being limited to single device to forming large arrays capable of mapping spatial information over extensive areas [25–29]. While addressing the challenge of uniformity remains ongoing, the progress in wearables is highly promising.

Despite these advancements, there are obvious limitations in the current wearable systems too: both analog front end (AFE) and processing unit that needed in a sensing system, largely remain the conventional, rigid, and bulky form factor that has persisted for decades. Components like amplifiers, filters, and analog-to-digital converters (ADCs) used in wearables nowadays are mostly off-the-shelf, relying on standard Silicon Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (Si CMOS) manufacturing and packaging technology. Only a few demonstrations have been made for flexible AFEs and processors, and their performance is still far behind those of Si CMOS. This raises challenges in their integration with sensors owing to the mechanical mismatch. On the other hand, the integration of the rigid components with flexible sensors, even in the platform of flexible printed circuit board (PCB), hinders the soft and close contact desired in wearable systems. The lack of mechanical flexibility in modules for interfacing the sensors and processing the sensory data hinders the development of truly flexible and conformable sensing systems for next-generation smart wearables.

Instead of focusing on the development of wearable sensors, this review paper aims to present a different picture composed of the latest developments that could complement the efforts dedicated in sensor design and development, for the purpose of realizing fully flexible sensing systems (Fig. 1). This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the advancement of flexible AFE made using novel materials. Section 3 offers a brief overview of system design. While mainly focusing on data transmission strategies, this section also discusses the aspects such as biocompatibility and permeability that are crucial for wearables. Section 4 then discusses the computing algorithms needed for wearables and their hardware implementation for sensing data processing using flexible electronics. By examining these recent advances, this paper aims to stimulate broader interest among researchers from relevant fields and ignite a more extensive discussion surrounding the future of flexible smart sensing systems in wearables.

Fig. 1. The conceptual scheme showing the fully flexible systems containing multimodal sensors, sensor front-end, processing unit, memory, display and communication modules, and the power system.

2. Flexible analog front-end for wearables

Despite long-standing efforts to improve the quality of wearable sensors, real-life sensing data is often subjected to unexpected disturbances and is imperfect: it contains noise, is suffering from baseline drift, is susceptible to hysteresis, and in many cases has a low signal-to-noise ratio. While it is possible to transmit all raw data to the cloud for further processing, the transmission bandwidth allocated in a wearable system is usually limited. The exponential increase of number of sensors in the wearable system exacerbates this issue, for example, to fulfill the requirements of mapping the spatiotemporal distribution of body metrics. This issue is further compounded by the signal loss and signal error during long-distance transmission, particularly when the sensors and interconnects are deformable during operation [8,30]. As a result, implementing local data pre-processing, i.e., via analog front-end, emerges as a more practical strategy. For instance, typical *ex vivo* electroencephalogram (EEG) data is measured in microvolts which, without sufficient amplification, renders the sensing signal difficult to read [31]. The same argument holds true for data processing as well.

Ideally, one could envision the next generation of wearable sensing systems to be fully conformable to the human skin, allowing for intimate human-machine interaction and accommodating to the twisting and stretching during motion [5–8], with autonomous power management [32], etc. This requires fabrication of every component, including sensors, sensing interfaces, processing units, power sources, and more, all on the soft substrate. Extensive efforts have been contributed to developing flexible sensors in the past decade or two [18–29]. However, the development of flexible ICs, for either sensing interface or sensory data processing and analysis, has been in its infancy and largely unmatching to the development of sensors. This is mainly due to the lack of scalability of electronic components, i.e., transistors, with highly controlled and uniform behavior. Without such prerequisites, large-scale electronic circuits and systems are challenging to realize. In this regard, this section provides an overview of recent advances in the development of nanomaterial based AFE.

Several classes of novel materials have been explored to build AFE components including amplifiers, filters and ADCs. Typical examples include organic semiconductors, metal oxides, carbon nanotubes, graphene, two-dimensional transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), etc. In general, a transistor of a large transconductance is preferred in order to obtain a higher gain—one genuine reason to explore novel materials for electronic applications. The use of novel materials on the polymeric substrate also enables a higher mechanical deformability, a highly favored trait for wearables, as it enables closer user interaction and leads to less user discomfort.

2.1. Technologies for flexible circuits

The construction of large-scale analog circuits, whether for use in portable systems or for more general purposes, requires large-scale uniform devices with controlled behaviors. To this end, it is essential to have thorough controls over several aspects of device fabrication, including material synthesis, material relocation onto the desired substrate, contact and dielectric control, and more. Among these, material synthesis is the first and most critical challenge to overcome. This refers not only to controlling the doping type and concentration to achieve high quality contact and enable CMOS design [33–35], but also to ensuring the material level uniformity over the entire area of interest [36–40]. The synthesis of single crystalline materials is highly advantageous in this respect, as it eliminates the unwanted randomness contribution from the domain boundary [39,41,42]. After synthesis, the material needs to be relocated from the donor to the desired location on the flexible substrate for device fabrication. This can be achieved by various methods, including transfer (2D materials) [43,44], PVD deposition (metal oxide) [45], printing/coating (organic semiconductors) [46–48], fluid-assisted, field-assisted or shear-force assisted alignment

(nanowires/nanotubes) [49,50], depending on the actual materials of interests. In particular, for quasi-1D materials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanowires (NWs), FETs based on multiple aligned wires/tubes are usually preferred over those based on a single wire/tube [51,52]. The former offers advantages such as higher on-state current (and hence higher driving capability) and more uniform behaviors between devices. However, this may also introduce deterioration in subthreshold slope of the FET due to the shielding effect arising from neighboring NWs/NTs. A compromise between these aspects is required. Achieving high quality devices also requires an ohmic contact with low contact resistance and a high-quality semiconductor-dielectric interface. In the last decade or two, many inspiring works have been done to reveal the potential to achieve low contact resistance, following strategies such as employing junctionless field-effect transistors structure [53], semiconductor-semimetal band hybridization [54], doping, chemisorbed monolayer treatment [55], etc. These efforts laid a strong foundation for the realization of electronics on a larger scale.

Flexibility and stretchability are two highly desired characteristics for wearable systems and the requirements to achieve them two have certain levels of similarities. For devices, flexibility is characterized by their capacity to withstand the strains that occur during bending while still maintaining the expected electrical response. The value of such strain depends on its relative position with respect to the neutral plane. Considering the simplest case where a uniform object (of rectangular shape) is bent at a bending radius of R , the strain at the surface (ε) could be characterized by its distance to the neutral plane, b , using the equation [56]:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{b}{R}.$$

Any strain exceeding the critical point that the material could withstand, would lead to mechanical failure. In practice, the scenario is more sophisticated because of the non-uniformity of materials and structures, the existence of defects, the environmental influence, and more. Nevertheless, in general, strategies for flexible device design include reducing the thickness of the device (e.g., to use quasi 1D or 2D materials), locating the device on the neutral plane, using materials that has low elastic modulus (e.g., soft organic materials that have cross-linked molecular chains with relatively weak molecular interactions) [57,58]. Similarly, stretchability is another area of interest; the maximum allowable strain is the indicator of the failure of a stretchable system. To increase the stretchability, two general strategies have been developed: a) employing soft materials with a low elastic modulus [58–60]; b) structure design at different levels (e.g., conductive nanomesh [61], serpentine-shaped interconnects [62]) to reduce the actual strain left on the brittle part of the system. It is worth noting that although devices of high flexibility/stretchability are preferred to build a wearable system, it does not necessarily mean that rigid components cannot be integrated. In fact, at the moment, many of the used components in wearables are still from the off-the-shelf and are bulky and rigid—they are only integrated onto the system with flexible/stretchable interconnects (i.e., flexible hybrid electronics), at the cost of local mechanical mismatch. Typical candidates for flexible/stretchable interconnects include metals (e.g., liquid, thin film, nanowires), oxides (e.g., indium tin oxide, reduced graphene oxide), inherently conductive polymers (e.g., polyaniline), conductive particle/polymer composites, and more, fabricated by methods such as deposition (PVD) and etching, printing, laser writing, etc [63]. Nevertheless, regardless of strategies employed in developing soft devices, there is likely a certain level of strain left on the materials during the mechanical deformations. Changes in electric potential (piezoelectric) or material resistivity (piezoresistive) under external strain are therefore an important aspect to be considered, if there is any. The modeling of these behaviors in wearables is therefore necessary [64]. Another aspect to be considered in the realization of interconnects is the power consumption and signal interference/delay. To this end, strategies have been developed to

reduce these unwanted effects such as material optimization (e.g., to reduce the resistance) [65], geometry optimization (e.g., from 2D to 3D to reduce the total length of interconnects and their capacitive coupling) [65,66], electromagnetic interference shielding [67,68], routing optimization (e.g., to minimize the crosstalk) [65], impedance matching (e.g., for antennas) [69], etc.

2.2. Amplification circuits for wearables

The amplifier is one of the fundamental elements in analog circuit design. Capable of amplifying a small signal to a larger one, they have been widely used as AFE for interfacing various sensors for signal readout. Typically, an amplifier is evaluated in terms of metrics such as gain, bandwidth, power consumption, etc. However, in many cases, these metrics are correlated and may not reach an optimum all together. The priority should be chosen according to the intended application. In a wearable system, the limitations come from aspects such as sensors that have a small signal output, the frequency range of both the real signal and the noise, the capacity of the power source, and so on. Even with mature Si CMOS technology, amplifier design is not a straight-forward task with all these limitations.

Replacing Si CMOS with novel materials to build amplifier ICs poses another layer of challenge. It is, for instance, owing to the limitation in materials, e.g., lack of complementary type of doping. To tackle this, efforts have been made to realize heterogeneous integration. One typical example is the integration of n-type metal-oxide and p-type organic semiconductor [70], either in 2D or in 3D manner. For those ICs realized on the flexible substrate, the fabrication limitations imposed by the polymeric substrates also notably affect the possible fabrication procedure that can be used, strictly restricting the processing temperature. In this regard, various novel fabrication techniques such as printing have been explored.

At the moment, the most explored amplifier design building from novel material is the single stage amplifiers (i.e., common source, common drain, common gate) [71–74]. Such an amplifier design offers the benefit of concise layout, but may have a limited operation range. Pseudo CMOS design that uses only single type of FETs but with comparable performance with respect to CMOS has also been proposed and widely explored [75–77].

While the realization of single stage amplifier is still relatively simple, the realization of other types of amplifiers poses notably more challenge, primarily because of the lack of yield and transistor matching. This inspires the researchers to come up with innovative circuit designs that can potentially compensate the shortcomings from lower levels. For example, one of the popular differential amplifier designs employs a long tail pair for common source noise removal. In the case that lacks n- or p-type candidate in the circuit, the unipolar inverter design has been widely explored in the past, with FETs of shorted gate-drain terminals or gate-source terminals acting as the load resistor. However, both strategies were found to result in a gain of ~ 10 or less when using organic thin-film transistors (TFTs). To further improve the circuit performance, the use of a.c. coupled load, composed of two transistors and one capacitor, has been developed. The demonstrated circuit exhibits a gain of ~ 200 , significantly higher than the previous two strategies. In addition, this loading design also offers a higher robustness to OFETs' metrics variations, resulting in a wide input voltage range [78]. For this strategy, the performance improvement, however, is at the cost of taking larger area owing to the introduction of capacitors. Another recently explored strategy is to use cascaded, multi-stage amplifier (Fig. 2a and b) to increase the gain, using the Indium gallium zinc oxide (IGZO) based TFTs. Thus, the gain from each stage does not need to be optimal, but a large overall gain can still be achieved. This also lessens the strict requirement in transistor performance matching and saves the occupied space at the same time [79].

While above mentioned analog amplifier based on organic and metal-oxide thin films has sparked research interest for more than a

Fig. 2. The demonstrations of various amplifier circuits. (a) and (b) The photograph of AFE circuits based on indium-gallium-zinc oxide (IGZO) TFTs. Adapt and reprint from ref. [79] with permission. Open Access. (c) The amplifier circuit based on organic thin-film transistors (OTFTs). Adapt and reprint from ref. [80] with permission. Open access. (d) and (e) The optical microscopy image and photograph of the epidermal electronic system based on single wall carbon nanotubes, which contains sensing, pre-processing and memory functions. Reprint from ref. [81] with permission. Open access. (f), (g) and (h) The photograph and the schematic illustration of the ultraflexible organic differential amplifier that can record electrocardiograms. Reprint from ref. [78] with permission. Copyright 2019 Springer Nature. (i) The photograph showing the printed proximity-sensing surface which includes sensor arrays and AFES. Reprint from ref. [82] with permission. Copyright 2022 Springer Nature.

decade (Fig. 2c), the use of other novel materials for amplifying application has only been reported recently. For example, the differential amplifier has been demonstrated using p-type CNT based FETs (Fig. 2d and e). Unlike previous work using organic semiconductor, a simple diode load is enough to obtain a gain of ~ 30 dB, partially owing to the high-performance achieved at the transistor level (e.g., standard deviation of 50 mV for threshold voltage) [81]. Some representative demonstrations of flexible amplifiers are shown in Fig. 2. Operational amplifier, a design more complicated than differential one, has been demonstrated using 2D MoS_2 [83]. The demonstrated operational amplifier can serve for various analog applications such as integrator, comparator, logarithmic and transimpedance amplifier, etc. The demonstrated gain is 43 dB with the carrier mobility of the FET ranging from 10 to $20 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$. Nevertheless, the potential

achievable mobility of MoS_2 can be far larger, as demonstrated by several recent reports [84]. In this regard, the 2D TMDs hold a good promise in realizing high gain amplifiers. On the other hand, various novel materials with different carrier mobility have been explored for the realization of amplifier circuits. They do not necessarily lead to a high gain owing to the mismatch of the transistors. In fact, many of the designs have to be tailored to accommodate the largely mismatched transistors, especially those on the flexible substrate. This is evidenced by the moderate value of gain achieved so far using novel materials (Table 1). In this regard, efforts both in transport study to further push the limit of single device and strategies in improving device-to-device uniformity are needed for medium- to large-scale circuit applications. This requires holistic optimization in material synthesis, transfer, and device engineering.

Table 1
Comparisons of amplifier circuits based on novel materials that can be used for wearables.

Material	Fabrication	Amplifier type	Gain	Bandwidth (3 dB gain)	V _{dd}	Power	Flexibility	Ref.
TIPS-Pentacene	Screen printing	Differential Amplifier	27 dB	~ 4 Hz	30 V	NA	Yes	[85]
DNTT ^a or its derivative DPh-DNTT	Stencil lithography	Operational amplifier	41.3 dB	130 Hz	4.5 V	7.2 μW	Yes	[86]
DNTT	Mask assisted deposition	differential amplifier	26.1 dB	~ 200 Hz	5 V	1.4 μW	Yes	[87]
SP500 Lisicon® polymer	Printing	Charge sensitive amplifier	~ 22 dB	~ 62 Hz	± 18 V	54 μW	Yes	[82]
DTBDT-C6 and PS	Printing	Common Source amplifier	~ 37 dB	NA	~ 2 V	NA	Yes	[80]
DNTT	Mask assisted evaporation	Differential Amplifier	35 dB	~ 27 Hz	4 V	NA	Yes	[78]
IGZO	PVD ^b	Operational amplifier	22.5 dB	~ 5600 Hz	5 V	160 μW	Yes	[77]
IGZO	PVD	Operational amplifier	18.7 dB	108 kHz	5 V	900 μW	Yes	[88]
IGZO	PVD	differential amplifier	14 dB	2000 Hz	NA	NA	Yes	[89]
IGZO	PVD	differential amplifier	21.5 dB	400 Hz	NA	NA	Yes	[89]
IGZO	PVD	differential amplifier	30 dB	150 Hz	NA	NA	Yes	[89]
IGZO	PVD	operational amplifier	29.5 dB	~ 9330 Hz	15 V	5.07 mW	No	[90]
IGZO	PVD	Differential Amplifier	~ 60 dB	1000 Hz	1.5 V	NA	Yes	[79]
CNT	PVD	differential amplifier	27 dB	~ 1000 Hz	NA	NA	Yes	[81]
MoS ₂	PVD	Operational amplifier	36 dB	~ 4000 Hz	10 V	NA	No	[83]

^a DNTT is short for dinaphtho[2,3-b:2',3'-f]thieno[3,2-b]thiophene.

^b PVD is short for physical vapor deposition.

Given the limitations imposed by real-life sensors, particularly those with a low signal level such as an electrocardiogram sensor, it is imperative that the noise is removed before further processing. The common mode noise can be eliminated by using a differential amplifier. A flexible differential amplifier based on organic semiconductors has been developed on foil and integrated with biosensors (see Fig. 2f and g). The results are inspiring for physiological signal monitoring, such as reading real-time electrocardiogram (ECG) signals from the human body (Fig. 2h). Another example worthy of mentioning is the charge-sensitive amplifier integrated with printed proximity-sensor. Using this design, a printed proximity-sensing surface composed of pyroelectric sensors and AFE ICs, all based on organic transistors, have been realized [82]. Despite showing a lesser gain, the sensing system has been scaled up to a 5×10 matrix (Fig. 2i). Such a system level demonstration cannot be successful without a high-quality and yield manufacturing of individual building blocks. For example, to achieve an 82 % working rate of the sensing pixels, this requires in total 768 defect-free devices. Despite being printed, the device manufacturing is currently carried out in a cleanroom environment (class, 10,000) to guarantee the interface quality and overlay control, compromising the advantage of printed electronics. In the future, efforts could be made to develop high-quality and uniform transistors in a non-cleanroom environment.

2.3. Noise removal

Noise removal is another key step in the pre-processing of sensor data, which requires dedicated components in the signal processing chain. This is particularly important when the amplitude of the sensing signal is comparable to the background noise. In this context, a common strategy is to use a filter so that certain frequency bands of the signal can be rejected. In general, filter circuits are classified into two types: active filters and passive filters. As the name implies, passive filters contain only passive components such as resistors and capacitors. A simple RC circuit can act as a low-pass filter, with its gain determined by the impedance of both components. Active filters, on the other hand, include active components in the circuit design. For example, the operational amplifier discussed above can be used to construct active filters with some additional passive components. The circuit complexity for active filters is much higher than for passive filters. However, active filters have advantages such as adjustability, low output impedance with no load effect. For wearable applications, both manufacturing

complexity and functionality have to be considered. Currently, most filters used in wearables are either off-the-shelf components or dedicated rigid chips fabricated using Si CMOS [91–94]. Software approaches such as neural networks and multivariate statistical analysis have also been employed in removing the motion-based artifacts. Only very limited work has been reported in realizing flexible filtering circuits. One work worth mentioning is the inkjet printed RC circuit based on 2D materials [95] — a passive filter. The circuit was realized on the paper substrate, which show its potential for application in wearables.

2.4. Analog-to-digital converter

The analog-to-digital converter (ADC) is typically the final stage of the AFE. Once the signal has been converted to digital format, it can be processed using digital signal processing techniques using mature digital components such as microcontrollers or Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). However, it is important to note that the A-to-D conversion process inevitably results in a loss of fidelity. While high-resolution conversion is always preferred, practical hardware limitations often impose restrictions. The choice of conversion resolution should be based on the back-end requirements. ADC performance is measured by metrics such as power consumption, speed, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and oversampling ratio. In a battery-powered or self-powered portable system (e.g., power harvested from thermal energy from the users, from the solar energy, or from motions, etc), the tight power budget also places requirements on the power consumption of each integrated component.

Various strategies have been developed for building ADCs, including flash ADC, half-flash ADC, successive approximation (SAR) ADC, delta-sigma ($\Delta\Sigma$) ADC, dual slope ADC, voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO)-based ADC, and more. Each strategy has its own advantages and disadvantages. For wearables, one should consider not only the application requirements for gain, power, speed, etc., but also the complexity of the hardware implementation. Flash ADCs compare the incoming signal with each digitized voltage level using a comparator, making them very hardware intensive as resolution increases (Fig. 3a). Their advantage is their high operating speed, as all comparisons are performed within one clock cycle. The half-flash ADC uses two flash ADCs to jointly convert the signal, reducing the components required in the design as the conversion resolution becomes high. However, this comes at the cost of reduced conversion speed compared to the flash ADC. SAR

Fig. 3. The scheme and demonstrations of ADCs for wearable applications. (a) and (b) The circuit diagram of flash ADC and SAR ADC, respectively. (c) and (d) The photograph of the flexible 6-bit SAR ADC using metal oxide TFTs. Adapt and reprint from ref. [98] with permission. Copyright 2018 IEEE. (e) The photograph showing the flexible ECG patch with sensing signal pre-processing functionality. Reprint from ref. [102] with permission. Open access.

ADCs use a comparison and implement the conversion in a strategy similar to the half-interval search algorithm in computer science (Fig. 3b). This design has a significant advantage in hardware cost over the previous two strategies, especially at high resolution. However, such a circuit takes longer to complete the conversion. The reduced

hardware cost in SAR ADC has led to many novel material-based ADCs adopting such a strategy [96–98] (Fig. 3c and d). While the above-mentioned ADCs' conversion strategies are all based on the voltage domain, there are also time-domain-based converters. A common type of time domain converter is the Δ - Σ ADC. This converter oversamples

the input signal at a frequency above the Nyquist rate and uses Δ - Σ modulation to approximate the analog value. The use of oversampling limits the speed of operation but has the advantage of reducing hardware cost and the ability to shape the noise—this makes Δ - Σ another popular circuit strategy using novel material-based electronics [99–101]. Another notable time-domain ADC is the VCO-based ADC or its variant. The strategies include using a voltage-controlled oscillator to represent analog voltage using oscillation frequency or a reset integrator to represent the signal of interest in modulated pulse width (Fig. 3e) [102]. By counting the frequency of pulse waves/duty cycle of the signal over a period of time, this method achieves A-to-D conversion. It shares the noise shaping advantage of the Δ - Σ ADC, but at the expense of a lower conversion speed.

From the fabrication point of view, the implementation of ADCs using novel materials and devices is more complicated than the aforementioned amplifiers and filters in terms of the number of active devices required to complete the circuit. This high requirement for the number of devices limits the demonstrations made so far, with most of the work limited to TFTs composed of organic semiconductors, metal oxide, and amorphous silicon. For instance, a flexible VCO-based ADC based on organic TFTs is realized using inkjet printing. The demonstrated resolution is 8-bit, with a sampling rate of 800 S/s [103] and power consumption of 800 μ W. Another team from Netherlands also explored the VCO-Based ADC using OTFTs, achieving a resolution of six bit and SNR is up to 48 dB [104]. Organic TFTs have also been used to realize Δ - Σ ADC with an integrator, a comparator and a level-shifter. The power consumption of the circuit is approximately 1.5 mW. With one bit resolution, it can achieve a high SNR of 26.5 dB [99]. One advantage of using organic semiconductors for realizing circuits is the availability of both n- and p- type semiconductors from the abundant material library from organics, thus enabling a CMOS design. However, at this stage, only a few works have realized the demonstration [105] while others focus on the unipolar circuit design employing only p-type OTFTs. On the other hand, metal oxides such as IGZO are another type of materials which have been explored for ADC applications. This includes efforts both from research laboratories [101] and industries such as Pragmatic and Imec [96,97], predominantly following SAR type of design. The benefit of metal oxide in material wise is its higher carrier mobility that can be achieved, compared to organic semiconductors. However, one critical drawback of this material is the lack of p-type candidates. Without a CMOS design, the power consumption could be much higher. And similar with organic semiconductors, its devices also suffer from surfaces states which can result in problems including bias stress, environmental instability, etc. Another material worthy of mentioning is poly- or amorphous Si thin films. The former holds a higher material quality and can reach a carrier mobility of $\sim 100 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V} \times \text{s}$ for both n- and p-type TFTs, while the latter has a modest mobility of $\sim 1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V} \times \text{s}$. The benefit of using Si based materials is its mature

fabrication process and thus a better transistor matching compared to other materials. Using these materials, flash ADCs have been realized with resolution up to five bits [106,107]. The comparison between ADCs realized with different materials and designs has been summarized in Table 2.

3. Data transmission and system design

The data collected from wearables and interfaced with an Analog Front End (AFE) can be used to derive insights and interpretations for various applications, such as health monitoring [108], environmental monitoring [109], point-of-care devices [110], AR (augmented reality)/VR (virtual reality) [111], robotics [112,113], and prosthetics [114]. Several solutions are available to achieve this goal with their own advantages and disadvantages. The common approach is to transmit data to a mobile phone using either wired or wireless strategies and to use off-the-wearable computing resources for data processing. For wired transmission, it usually involves the USB protocol: for example, the USB On-the-Go (OTG) being used in modern smartphones. This interface enables smartphones to act as power sources or hosts. Smartphones that are compatible with USB OTG can connect to various USB devices and electronic boards that support the USB interface. This allows for battery-free operation of the sensing system by providing a 5 V power supply. But today, all the USB module developed so far is rigid, posing restrictions in mechanical compliance of the whole system.

An alternative strategy for transmitting data involves wireless methods. Currently, Bluetooth technology has emerged as the dominant protocol for establishing connections between smartphones and external sensing systems within a range below 10 m. Its versatility is evident in numerous wearable sensing applications ranging from bio-sensor systems to healthcare and environmental monitoring. Operating at data transmission rates on the order of megabits per second (Mb/s), traditional Bluetooth consumes several milliwatts of power. The subsequent introduction of Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) addresses the need for improved power efficiency, particularly for applications with intermittent communication needs and limited power resources. Optimized for short-range communication with bursty data transmission, BLE meets the needs of wearables by enabling extended device operation without frequent battery replacement. Despite these advantages, both traditional Bluetooth and BLE have limitations, including potential security vulnerabilities and susceptibility to interference in crowded signal environments. These concerns are particularly important for wearables given their potential to collect sensitive user information, underscoring the critical importance of addressing privacy and security challenges as wearable technology evolves [115].

Near Field Communication, on the other hand, is a short-range technology that typically has a communication range of about 10

Table 2
Comparisons of different flexible ADCs.

Material	Fabrication	ADC type	Resolution	Sampling rate	SNDR(SNR)	V _{dd}	Power	Ref.
Organic (pentacene)	NA	Δ - Σ	NA	NA	24.5 dB	15 V	$\sim 1.5 \text{ mW}$	[99,100]
Organic	NA	VCO	6 bit	NA	48 dB (SNR)	NA	$\sim 48 \mu\text{W}$	[104]
Metal oxide	PVD with Printed Interconnects	VCO	3–6 bit	800 S/s	17–40 dB	NA	$\sim 800 \mu\text{W}$	[103]
Metal oxide (IGZO)	PVD	SAR	7.8 bit	100 S/s	NA		2.93 mW	[96]
Metal oxide (IGZO)	PVD	SAR	6 bit	13 or 26 S/s	37.1 dB	15 V	49 μW	[97]
Metal oxide (IGZO)	PVD	Δ - Σ	11 bit	NA	69.68 dB	10 V	0.15 $\mu\text{J}/\text{conversion step}$	[101]
Metal-oxide (IGZO)	PVD	SAR	5 bit	26.67 S/s	35.9 dB	NA	73 μW	[98]
Si (Poly)	PVD with laser crystallization	Flash	3 bit	3 M S/s	NA	13 V	NA	[107]
Si (Amorphous)	PVD	Flash	5 bit	2000 S/s	NA	10 V	13.6 mW	[106]

Fig. 4. Various data transmission method used in wearables. (a) A self-powered, sweat monitoring system with BLE as the data transmission method. Reprint from ref. [116] with permission. Open access. (b) A smart acousto-mechanical sensing (BAMS) system for physiological monitoring and diagnostics. The BLE module was integrated for data transmission. Adapted from ref. [117] with permission. Copyright 2023 Springer Nature. (c) A smart bandage that can sense the strain and temperature of its user and transmit the sensing data using NFC. Reprint from ref. [118] with permission. Open access. (d) A flexible NFC chip fabricated by imec. Reprint from ref. [120] with permission. Copyright 2016 IEEE.

centimeters and uses electromagnetic induction between NFC-enabled devices in close proximity. In passive mode, NFC is distinguished by the fact that it does not rely on an external battery; instead, power is transmitted through inductive coupling. This characteristic makes NFC particularly attractive in scenarios where the convenience of wireless communication is combined with simplified power management, offering significant advantages in terms of efficiency and ease of use. However, it is important to be aware of its limitations, particularly in handling large amounts of data, where NFC can face challenges due to its limited transmission speed - operating at a frequency of 13.56 MHz, NFC has a transmission speed of approximately 400 kb/s. Despite this limitation, NFC's unique characteristics make it a compelling choice for smart wearables. The NFC module usually contains two aspects, the antenna for data transmission and the chip for data storage. The antenna can be made fully flexible, while the chip for data storage is, at the moment, mostly in the rigid form factor (Fig. 4a–c) [116–118]. Fortunately, with the advances in flexible TFTs technologies, some initial demonstrations have been made to realize NFC transponder chip on the flexible substrate, by using metal oxides as the active materials. Owing to the limitation in metal-oxides, p-type candidate is not available. Unipolar logic circuit design has to be used to overcome this issue. The first demonstration in the world, in fact, was demonstrated on the glass substrate, with power consumption of $\sim 20 \mu\text{W}$ at a voltage bias of 5 V [119] but a limited transmission speed of $\sim 0.05 \text{ kb/s}$. The flexible version was demonstrated on the foils, with a higher transmission speed up to $\sim 70 \text{ kb/s}$ [120] (Fig. 4d). The realization of the flexible NFC chip could potentially be integrated onto wearables for data transmission applications [121].

During the data transmission, concerns also arise regarding security and privacy violations. The issue is compounded by the limited transmission bandwidth inherent in wireless transmission protocols, particularly when dealing with systems featuring a large number of sensors

(e.g., in the number of hundreds of thousands of sensors). These issues can be addressed by the strategies discussed in the next section.

A more common strategy for sensing data pre-processing and communication is to use flexible PCB to house the off-the-shelf (rigid) components. This strategy is fascinating as it could provide a certain level of mechanical flexibility needed in wearable systems, while taking advantage of mature Si CMOS technology. A large number of demonstrations have been made in the past one decade or two. Some examples include the flexible sensor patch for various applications including sweat analysis (Fig. 4a) [116], cardiorespiratory and gastrointestinal monitoring (Fig. 4b) [117], strain and temperature monitoring (Fig. 4c) [118], and more [122,123]. For both the cases shown in Fig. 4a and b, the BLE module has been used for data transmission while in the case shown in Fig. 4c, a commercial NFC chip has been employed. These solutions rely on the rigid off-the-shell component, which lead to the locally mechanical hard spot on the system and prevent a fully intimate user-machine interaction.

Except from the data transmission, in general, there are several requirements to meet when designing a smart wearable system: 1) The collected signal should be of sufficient quality for the intended applications. The indicator to be used for measuring the data quality varies from case to case depending on the actual physiological parameters to be collected. For example, for the electroencephalography (EEG) signal, the quality is measured by the signal-to-noise ratio and is influenced by various factors, including the contact electrodes and the environment, the integrated AFE circuits, and more. For biosensors, the quality and the accuracy of the data are measured by sensitivity and specificity, reflecting the true positive and true negative test rate, respectively. Therefore, depending on the intended use, the material, device, and system should be co-designed, to ensure the high quality of collected data. 2) The frequency of data collection should be high enough to provide as much information as needed, but as low as possible to

Fig. 5. Flexible or potentially flexible system for smart sensory data processing. (a) The schematic and function diagram of the flexible machine learning engine for electronic nose application. Reprint from ref. [134] with permissions. Open access. (b) Optical microscopy image and the schematic illustration of the functional cell made using MoS₂ based transistors that can perform multiplication function. (c) The circuit level illustration of how the MoS₂ based system can perform matrix multiplication. (b) and (c) are adapted and reprinted from ref. [137] with permission. Open access. (d) The scheme and demonstration of associative learning using printed synaptic transistor. Adapt and reprint from ref. [140] with permission. Copyright 2022 AAAS. (e) The scheme of OTFT and the photograph of flexible synaptic circuit demonstrated using OTFT. Adapted from ref. [141] with permission. Open access. (f) The Axon-Hillock circuit demonstrated using OECTs and its encoding behavior. Reprint from ref. [142] with permission. Open access. (g) The smart sensing system that includes a nanowire based sensor and nanowire based memristor for encoding the sensing data. Reprint from ref. [143] with permission. Open access.

minimize the energy consumption for testing and data transmission. Again, this is a system design issue that needs to be considered holistically in terms of power allocation and consumption, amount and size of data to be collected, user habits, and more. 3) Needless to say, the wearable devices and system should be biocompatible. For biocompatibility test, regardless of the types and applications of the wearables, most should be evaluated by cytotoxicity, irritation, and sensitization testing as the minimum, following ISO 10993 [124]. For example, wearable sensors usually employ printed carbon or silver inks for conductive electrodes. The study of the leaching behavior of these printed inks and the associated toxicity can be inspiring [125]. The biocompatibility tests are typically performed *in vitro*, but depending on the intended use of the wearables, animal tests can also be critical; 4) For long term use, the wearables should also be permeable. The permeability ensures the easy dissipation of heat, moisture, metabolic wastes, etc, maintaining the thermophysiological requirements of the human body and providing a notable increase in user experience. The permeability is achieved normally by structural design ranging from material level to system level, and can be measured through parameters such as water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) as per ASTM E96 testing standard [126], oxygen transmission rate (OTR) as per ASTM D3985 standard [127], carbon dioxide transmission rate (COTR) as per ASTM D1434 standard [128], and more.

4. Data processing and encoding

To address the challenges related to data transmission, there has been a shift towards localized on-wearable processing. In fact, the exploration of wearable computers began in the late 20th century, characterized by their lightweight and portable nature, albeit lacking flexibility [9,10,129,130]. This rigidity impedes the seamless interaction between humans and wearable systems. Recent efforts to develop microprocessors on the flexible substrates have shown initial success [131], although the computing power, as well as the power consumption, still lags behind that of rigid counterparts, imposing certain restrictions on the capabilities of these flexible systems.

If we take a step back, we can see that the data processing task required for wearables does not require an integrated general-purpose processor. It is far more than enough. From a software point of view, the algorithms designed for implementation in wearable sensing systems do not even need to be general-purpose but should be specific enough to perform one or more related tasks in wearables using the collected sensing data. These include monitoring applications for health and fitness tracking (e.g., sleep pattern recognition, emotion recognition, disease detection, and hydration status monitoring), motion detection applications for activities like fall prevention, as well as object tracking and recognition for AR and VR experiences enabled by smart glasses. To handle these tasks, various machine learning algorithms are available [132,133]: Classification tasks, like those involved in health and fitness monitoring, can be addressed using algorithms such as decision trees, support vector machines, and neural networks. Regression, on the other hand, is needed in predicting continuous parameters, as seen in applications like estimating calorie consumption and predicting blood pressure. Support vector regression and neural network algorithms prove useful in this context. Furthermore, unsupervised learning algorithms, including K-Means Clustering, Hierarchical Clustering, and Gaussian Mixture Model, find application in clustering sensory data. These algorithms provide valuable insights into user behavior, health patterns, contextual information, and more. The unique nature of wearables, which often prioritizes portability, wearability, and energy efficiency, necessitates a careful balance in functionality of the algorithm and the implementation difficulties in the computing hardware for wearables.

From a hardware point of view, most of past demonstrations of system-on-chip for running the above-mentioned algorithms for smart sensing are based on standard Si CMOS and implemented on the rigid

substrate only. This notably influenced the user experience. Realizing a fully flexible hardware system capable of implementing the mentioned algorithms poses a considerable challenge. One viable strategy in this endeavor is the adoption of algorithm-hardware co-design, a technique that effectively reduces the complexity of the hardware needed to execute algorithms. Simultaneously, researchers are actively exploring methods to enhance the fabrication of flexible transistors, aiming for improved performance control to facilitate the development of more intricate circuits and systems. A noteworthy example in this context is the machine learning engine demonstrated by Pragmatic Semiconductor and ARM (Fig. 5a) [134,135]. This flexible system has the capability to execute algorithms such as decision trees and multilayer perceptrons. Integrated with flexible gas sensors and a sensing interface, this system can be applied to tasks like malodour classification. While this demonstration primarily focuses on digital design, efforts have also been directed towards realizing analog systems. This releases the need for ADCs from the system. For instance, researchers have implemented hardwired neural networks in textiles using off-the-shelf components, interconnected with highly conductive threads on the textile [136]. Additionally, the exploration of nanomaterials, such as 2D MoS₂ and 1D nanowire-based multigate FET, has led to the development of circuits capable of matrix multiplication operations [137-139] (Fig. 5b and c). The large-scale integration of these circuits, along with modules functioning as activation functions and memory, has resulted in the creation of hardware neural networks. Although the demonstrated work is currently on rigid substrates, with suitable material transferring technologies, it holds the potential for application on flexible substrates like polyimide.

Recent research has explored the use of novel nanodevices to emulate synapse functionality, i.e., synaptic devices [144]. This exploration could be exploited to demonstrate the learning rule observed in biological nervous system, for example, the time-based learning rules (Spiking time dependent plasticity) on the device level [145]. This is a representative unsupervised learning rule that correlates inputs with outputs. The implementation of such a learning rule and its derivatives can be achieved using flexible synaptic transistor [140], but with the support of peripheral circuits that are still rigid at the moment (Fig. 5d). An all-flexible demonstration can be potentially achieved using more matured metal-oxide TFT technology to realize the periphery circuit. Traditionally, synaptic circuits have also been developed to emulate such a function in Si CMOS. In fact, efforts have also been made in using organic TFT based circuitry to implement the same on the flexible substrate (Fig. 5e) [141]. The exploration of these advancements suggests a promising future for flexible processing systems in the field of wearable electronics.

The focus of the preceding discussion is primarily on the processing of data collected by sensors. However, there is also significant research effort devoted to encoding sensed data, particularly in the context of spiking neural networks, where tactile inputs are represented as spikes. Pioneering work in this area is currently focused on the use of organic TFT-based circuits to implement designs such as voltage-controlled oscillation circuits, as shown in ref. [146], axon hillock circuits, as shown in ref. [142] (Fig. 5f), and memristor device based circuit, as shown in ref. [143] (Fig. 5g). In addition, the integration of organic thin-film transistors (TFTs) on flexible substrates adds flexibility to the system, while the use of neural coding circuits mimics the biological language of communication. The combination of these two features ignites a promising evolution of wearables that can lead to the next generation of bioimplants and neuroprosthetics.

5. Conclusion

After decades of dedicated research and innovation, the field of wearables has undergone a transformative journey, evolving from rigid structures to soft, conformable forms, and from single or limited sensors

to large-scale arrays covering considerable areas, from heavy reliance on external power sources to achieving self-sustainability and energy autonomy. This remarkable evolution owes much to breakthroughs in disciplines such as printed and flexible electronics, nanoscience and technology. These advances have begun to enable an exciting paradigm shift — from flexible hybrid electronics, which combines flexible sensors with rigid CMOS components, to fully flexible systems. Moreover, the groundbreaking developments in neuromorphic devices and circuits using novel materials open up unprecedented possibilities for wearables and extending their applications to neurorobotics and neuroprosthetics. While this paper reviews some recent advancements in the area of flexible circuits and systems for sensing interfaces, data processing, and data encoding, it does not encompass the entirety of noteworthy advances in this expansive field. For a more comprehensive overview of wearables, several previous papers are well worth reading. To name a few: ref. [19] focuses on the advances in pressure sensors for health and robotic applications; ref. [132] offers a comprehensive review on wearable market; ref. [120] provides an in-depth overview of the wearable system with a focus on clinical diagnostics; ref. [147] has an emphasis on data collection and data analysis; ref. [148] draws a technology roadmap for flexible sensors. By contrast, the paper presented here aims to provide a distinctive perspective that sheds light on the immense potential of fully flexible circuits and systems for wearable applications.

Funding

This work was funded by the European Union through Marie Curie Global Fellowship: HORIZON-MSCA-2022-PF-01-01, Neuro-encoded electronic skin (NEUCODES), [Grant agreement ID: 101111036].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fengyuan Liu: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Leandro Lorenzelli:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work the authors used DeepL in order to proofread and polish the writing. After using DeepL, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Acknowledgments

N/A.

References

- [1] T. Someya, Z. Bao, G.G. Malliaras, The rise of plastic bioelectronics, *Nature* 540 (2016) 379–385.
- [2] S. Abdelwahab, B. Hamdaoui, M. Guizani, A. Rayes, Enabling smart cloud services through remote sensing: an internet of everything enabler, *IEEE Internet Things J.* 1 (2014) 276–288.
- [3] R. Dahiya, N. Yogeswaran, F. Liu, L. Manjakkal, E. Burdet, V. Hayward, H. Jörmteell, Large-area soft e-skin: the challenges beyond sensor designs, *Proc. IEEE* 107 (2019) 2016–2033.
- [4] L. Portilla, K. Loganathan, H. Faber, A. Eid, J.G. Hester, M.M. Tentzeris, M. Fattori, E. Cantatore, C. Jiang, A. Nathan, Wirelessly powered large-area electronics for the Internet of Things, *Nat. Electron* 6 (2023) 10–17.
- [5] T.R. Ray, J. Choi, A.J. Bandodkar, S. Krishnan, P. Gutfur, L. Tian, R. Ghaffari, J.A. Rogers, Bio-integrated wearable systems: a comprehensive review, *Chem. Rev.* 119 (2019) 5461–5533.
- [6] J. Choi, R. Ghaffari, L.B. Baker, J.A. Rogers, Skin-interfaced systems for sweat collection and analytics, *Sci. Adv.* 4 (2018) eaar3921.
- [7] D. Son, Z. Bao, Nanomaterials in skin-inspired electronics, Toward soft and robust skin-like electronic nanosystems, *ACS Nano* 12 (2018) 11731–11739.
- [8] M. Bariya, Nyein HYY, A. Javey, Wearable sweat sensors, *Nat. Electron.* 1 (2018) 160–171.
- [9] E.O. Thorp, The invention of the first wearable computer, *Digest of Papers. Second International Symposium on Wearable Computers (Cat. No. 98EX215)*, IEEE, 1998, pp. 4–8.
- [10] E. Thorp, A favorable strategy for twenty-one, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 47 (1961) 110–112, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.47.1.110>.
- [11] S. Lee, S. Shin, S. Lee, J. Seo, J. Lee, S. Son, H.J. Cho, H. Algadi, S. Al-Sayari, D.E. Kim, Ag nanowire reinforced highly stretchable conductive fibers for wearable electronics, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 25 (2015) 3114–3121.
- [12] W. Zeng, L. Shu, Q. Li, S. Chen, F. Wang, X.M. Tao, Fiber-based wearable electronics: a review of materials, fabrication, devices, and applications. *Adv. Mater.* 26 (2014) 5310–5336.
- [13] X. Shi, Y. Zuo, P. Zhai, J. Shen, Y. Yang, Z. Gao, M. Liao, J. Wu, J. Wang, X. Xu, Large-area display textiles integrated with functional systems, *Nature* 591 (2021) 240–245.
- [14] G. Loke, W. Yan, T. Khudiyev, G. Noel, Y. Fink, Recent progress and perspectives of thermally drawn multimaterial fiber electronics, *Adv. Mater.* 32 (2020) 1904911.
- [15] X. Zhao, Y. Zhou, J. Xu, G. Chen, Y. Fang, T. Tat, X. Xiao, Y. Song, S. Li, J. Chen, Soft fibers with magnetoelasticity for wearable electronics, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 6755.
- [16] A. Fakhruddin, H. Li, F. Di Giacomo, T. Zhang, N. Gasparini, A.Y. Elezabi, A. Mohanty, A. Ramadoss, J. Ling, A. Soultati, Fiber-shaped electronic devices, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021) 2101443.
- [17] L. Manjakkal, A. Pullanchiyodan, N. Yogeswaran, E.S. Hosseini, R. Dahiya, A wearable supercapacitor based on conductive PEDOT: PSS-coated cloth and a sweat electrolyte, *Adv. Mater.* 32 (2020) 1907254.
- [18] W. Cheng, X. Wang, Z. Xiong, J. Liu, Z. Liu, Y. Jin, H. Yao, T.-S. Wong, J.S. Ho, B.C. Tee, Frictionless multiphase interface for near-ideal aero-elastic pressure sensing, *Nat. Mater.* 22 (2023) 1352–1360.
- [19] S.R.A. Ruth, V.R. Feig, H. Tran, Z. Bao, Microengineering pressure sensor active layers for improved performance, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 30 (2020) 2003491.
- [20] C.B. Cooper, S.E. Root, L. Michalek, S. Wu, J.-C. Lai, M. Khatib, S.T. Oyakhire, R. Zhao, J. Qin, Z. Bao, Autonomous alignment and healing in multilayer soft electronics using immiscible dynamic polymers, *Science* 380 (2023) 935–941.
- [21] X. Meng, Y. Qiao, C. Do, W. Bras, C. He, Y. Ke, T.P. Russell, D. Qiu, Hysteresis-free nanoparticle-reinforced hydrogels, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2108243.
- [22] L. Bannenberg, H. Schreuders, B. Dam, Tantalum-palladium, hysteresis-free optical hydrogen sensor over 7 orders of magnitude in pressure with sub-second response. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 31 (2021) 2010483, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202010483>.
- [23] F. Xue, Q. Peng, R. Ding, P. Li, X. Zhao, H. Zheng, L. Xu, Z. Tang, X. Zhang, X. He, Ultra-sensitive, highly linear, and hysteresis-free strain sensors enabled by gradient stiffness sliding strategy, *npj Flex. Electron.* 8 (2024) 14.
- [24] J. Zhang, N. Mu, L. Liu, J. Xie, H. Feng, J. Yao, T. Chen, W. Zhu, Highly sensitive detection of malignant glioma cells using metamaterial-inspired THz biosensor based on electromagnetically induced transparency, *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 185 (2021) 113241.
- [25] Q.-B. Zhu, B. Li, D.-D. Yang, C. Liu, S. Feng, M.-L. Chen, Y. Sun, Y.-N. Tian, X. Su, X.-M. Wang, A flexible ultrasensitive optoelectronic sensor array for neuromorphic vision systems, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 1798.
- [26] H. Oh, G.-C. Yi, M. Yip, S.A. Dayeh, Scalable tactile sensor arrays on flexible substrates with high spatiotemporal resolution enabling slip and grip for closed-loop robotics, *Sci. Adv.* 6 (2020) eabd7795.
- [27] A.U. Alam, D. Clyne, H. Jin, N.-X. Hu, M.J. Deen, Fully integrated, simple, and low-cost electrochemical sensor array for in situ water quality monitoring, *ACS Sens.* 5 (2020) 412–422.
- [28] M. Li, J. Chen, W. Zhong, M. Luo, W. Wang, X. Qing, Y. Lu, Q. Liu, K. Liu, Y. Wang, Large-area, wearable, self-powered pressure–temperature sensor based on 3D thermoelectric spacer fabric, *ACS Sens.* 5 (2020) 2545–2554.
- [29] W. Lin, B. Wang, G. Peng, Y. Shan, H. Hu, Z. Yang, Skin-inspired piezoelectric tactile sensor array with crosstalk-free row + column electrodes for spatiotemporally distinguishing diverse stimuli, *Adv. Sci.* 8 (2021) 2002817.
- [30] F. Liu, S. Deswal, A. Christou, Y. Sandamirskaya, M. Kholi, R. Dahiya, Neuro-inspired electronic skin for robots, *Sci. Robot.* 7 (2022) eabl7344.
- [31] S. Suiy, Y. Li, Y. Zhang, *EEG Signal Analysis and Classification*, first ed., Springer Cham, 2016 10.1007/978-3-319-47653-7.
- [32] L. Roselli, N.B. Carvalho, F. Alimenti, P. Mezzanotte, G. Orecchini, M. Virili, C. Mariotti, R. Goncalves, P. Pinho, Smart surfaces: large area electronics systems for Internet of Things enabled by energy harvesting, *Proc. IEEE* 102 (2014) 1723–1746.
- [33] N.H. Van, J.-H. Lee, J.I. Sohn, S.N. Cha, D. Whang, J.M. Kim, D.J. Kang, High performance Si nanowire field-effect-transistors based on a CMOS inverter with tunable threshold voltage, *Nanoscale* 6 (2014) 5479–5483.
- [34] B. Zhao, B. Gothe, M. Sarcletti, Y. Zhao, T. Rejek, X. Liu, H. Park, P. Strohriegl, M. Halik, Wafer-scale organic complementary inverters fabricated with self-assembled monolayer field-effect transistors, *Adv. Electron. Mater.* 6 (2020) 2000515.
- [35] K.P.O. Brien, C.J. Dorow, A. Penumatcha, K. Maxey, S. Lee, C.H. Naylor, A. Hsiao, B. Holybee, C. Rogan, D. Adams, Advancing 2D monolayer CMOS through contact, channel and interface engineering, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)* 11–16 Dec. 2021, pp. 7.1.1–7.1.4.

- [36] R. Hu, S. Xu, J. Wang, Y. Shi, J. Xu, K. Chen, L. Yu, Unprecedented uniform 3d growth integration of 10-layer stacked si nanowires on tightly confined sidewall grooves, *Nano Lett.* 20 (2020) 7489–7497.
- [37] M. Liu, Y. Liu, J. Dong, Y. Bai, W. Gao, S. Shang, X. Wang, J. Kuang, C. Du, Y. Zou, J. Chen, Y. Liu, Two-dimensional covalent organic framework films prepared on various substrates through vapor induced conversion, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 1411, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-29050-9>.
- [38] Y. Xia, X. Chen, J. Wei, S. Wang, S. Chen, S. Wu, M. Ji, Z. Sun, Z. Xu, W. Bao, 12-inch growth of uniform MoS₂ monolayer for integrated circuit manufacture, *Nat. Mater.* 22 (2023) 1324–1331.
- [39] H. Jiang, W. Hu, The emergence of organic single-crystal electronics, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 59 (2020) 1408–1428.
- [40] G. Kitahara, S. Inoue, T. Higashino, M. Ikawa, T. Hayashi, S. Matsuoka, S. Arai, T. Hasegawa, Meniscus-controlled printing of single-crystal interfaces showing extremely sharp switching transistor operation, *Sci. Adv.* 6 (2020) eabc8847.
- [41] T. Li, W. Guo, L. Ma, W. Li, Z. Yu, Z. Han, S. Gao, L. Liu, D. Fan, Z. Wang, Epitaxial growth of wafer-scale molybdenum disulfide semiconductor single crystals on sapphire, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 16 (2021) 1201–1207.
- [42] Y. Gong, B. Li, G. Ye, S. Yang, X. Zou, S. Lei, Z. Jin, E. Bianco, S. Vinod, B.I. Yakobson, Direct growth of MoS₂ single crystals on polyimide substrates, *2D Mater.* 4 (2017) 021028.
- [43] H. Kim, Y. Liu, K. Lu, C.S. Chang, D. Sung, M. Akl, K. Qiao, K.S. Kim, B.-I. Park, M. Zhu, High-throughput manufacturing of epitaxial membranes from a single wafer by 2D materials-based layer transfer process, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 18 (2023) 464–470.
- [44] R. Frisenda, E. Navarro-Moratalla, P. Gant, D.P. De Lara, P. Jarillo-Herrero, R.V. Gorbachev, A. Castellanos-Gomez, Recent progress in the assembly of nano-devices and van der Waals heterostructures by deterministic placement of 2D materials, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 47 (2018) 53–68.
- [45] T. Ohno, Thin-film PVD: materials, processes, and equipment, *Flat Panel Disp. Manuf.* (2018) 209–224.
- [46] G.-P. Rigas, M.M. Payne, J.E. Anthony, P.N. Horton, F.A. Castro, M. Shkunov, Spray printing of organic semiconducting single crystals, *Nat. Commun.* 7 (2016) 13531.
- [47] Y. Diao, B.C. Tee, G. Giri, J. Xu, D.H. Kim, H.A. Becerril, R.M. Stoltenberg, T.H. Lee, G. Xue, S.C. Mannsfeld, Solution coating of large-area organic semiconductor thin films with aligned single-crystalline domains, *Nat. Mater.* 12 (2013) 665–671.
- [48] C. Koutsiaiki, T. Kaimakamis, A. Zachariadis, A. Papamichail, C. Kamaraki, S. Fachouri, C. Gravalidis, A. Laskarakis, S. Logothetidis, Efficient combination of Roll-to-Roll compatible techniques towards the large area deposition of a polymer dielectric film and the solution-processing of an organic semiconductor for the field-effect transistors fabrication on plastic substrate, *Org. Electron.* 73 (2019) 231–239.
- [49] Y. Chen, T. Liang, L. Chen, Y. Chen, B.-R. Yang, Y. Luo, G.-S. Liu, Self-assembly, alignment, and patterning of metal nanowires, *Nanoscale Horiz.* 7 (2022) 1299–1339.
- [50] Y. Sun, T. Dong, L. Yu, J. Xu, K. Chen, Planar growth, integration, and applications of semiconducting nanowires, *Adv. Mater.* 32 (2020) 1903945.
- [51] K. Takei, T. Takahashi, J.C. Ho, H. Ko, A.G. Gillies, P.W. Leu, R.S. Fearing, A. Javey, Nanowire active-matrix circuitry for low-voltage macroscale artificial skin, *Nat. Mater.* 9 (2010) 821–826.
- [52] C. Jia, Z. Lin, Y. Huang, X. Duan, Nanowire electronics: from nanoscale to macroscale, *Chem. Rev.* 119 (2019) 9074–9135.
- [53] J.-P. Colinge, C.-W. Lee, A. Afzalani, N.D. Akhavan, R. Yan, I. Ferain, P. Razavi, B. O'Neill, A. Blake, M. White, Nanowire transistors without junctions, *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 5 (2010) 225–229.
- [54] W. Li, X. Gong, Z. Yu, L. Ma, W. Sun, S. Gao, Ç. Koroğlu, W. Wang, L. Liu, T. Li, Approaching the quantum limit in two-dimensional semiconductor contacts, *Nature* 613 (2023) 274–279.
- [55] J.W. Borchert, R.T. Weitz, S. Ludwigs, H. Klauk, A critical outlook for the pursuit of lower contact resistance in organic transistors, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2104075.
- [56] L. Mao, Q. Meng, A. Ahmad, Z. Wei, Mechanical analyses and structural design requirements for flexible energy storage devices, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 7 (2017) 1700535.
- [57] Z. Suo, E.Y. Ma, H. Gleskova, S. Wagner, Mechanics of rollable and foldable film-on-foil electronics, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 74 (1999) 1177–1179.
- [58] H. Li, Y. Ma, Y. Huang, Material innovation and mechanics design for substrates and encapsulation of flexible electronics: a review, *Mater. Horiz.* 8 (2021) 383–400.
- [59] W. Wang, S. Wang, R. Rastak, Y. Ochiai, S. Niu, Y. Jiang, P.K. Arunachala, Y. Zheng, J. Xu, N. Matsuhashi, X. Yan, Strain-insensitive intrinsically stretchable transistors and circuits, *Nat. Electron.* 4 (2021) 143–150.
- [60] S. Wang, J. Xu, W. Wang, G.J.N. Wang, R. Rastak, F. Molina-Lopez, J.W. Chung, S. Niu, V.R. Feig, J. Lopez, T. Lei, Skin electronics from scalable fabrication of an intrinsically stretchable transistor array, *Nature* 555 (2018) 83–88.
- [61] W. Dang, V. Vinciguerra, L. Lorenzelli, R. Dahiya, Printable stretchable interconnects, *Flex. Print. Electron.* 2 (2017) 013003, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2058-8585/aa5ab2>.
- [62] Y. Sun, W.G. Chong, Structural engineering of electrodes for flexible energy storage devices, *Mater. Horiz.* 10 (2023) 2373–2397.
- [63] T. Agcayazi, K. Chatterjee, A. Bozkurt, T.K. Ghosh, Flexible interconnects for electronic textiles, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 3 (2018) 1700277.
- [64] S. Yong, K. Aw, Modeling electrical resistance behavior of soft and flexible piezoresistive sensors based on carbon-black/silicone elastomer composites, *Sens. Imaging* 23 (2022) 22.
- [65] R.K. Baruah, H. Yoo, E.K. Lee, Interconnection technologies for flexible electronics: materials, fabrications, and applications, *Micromachines* 14 (2023) 1131.
- [66] P. Ren, J. Dong, Direct fabrication of VIA interconnects by electrohydrodynamic printing for multi-layer 3D flexible and stretchable electronics, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 6 (2021) 2100280.
- [67] Z. Nan, W. Wei, Z. Lin, J. Chang, Y. Hao, Flexible nanocomposite conductors for electromagnetic interference shielding, *Nano-Micro Lett.* 15 (2023) 172.
- [68] J. Cheng, C. Li, Y. Xiong, H. Zhang, H. Raza, S. Ullah, J. Wu, G. Zheng, Q. Cao, D. Zhang, Q. Zheng, Recent advances in design strategies and multifunctionality of flexible electromagnetic interference shielding materials, *Nano-Micro Lett.* 14 (2022) 80.
- [69] M.J. Christoe, J. Han, K. Kalantar, Zadeh, Telecommunications and data processing in flexible electronic systems, *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 5 (2020) 1900733.
- [70] G. Woo, H. Yoo, T. Kim, Hybrid thin-film materials combinations for complementary integration circuit implementation, *Membranes* 11 (2021) 931.
- [71] Z. Luo, B. Peng, J. Zeng, Z. Yu, Y. Zhao, J. Xie, R. Lan, Z. Ma, L. Pan, K. Cao, Y. Lu, D. He, H. Ning, W. Meng, Y. Yang, X. Chen, W. Li, J. Wang, D. Pan, X. Tu, W. Huo, X. Huang, D. Shi, L. Li, M. Liu, Y. Shi, X. Feng, P. Chan, X. Wang, Sub-thermionic, ultra-high-gain organic transistors and circuits, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 1928, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22192-2>.
- [72] L. Petti, N. Münzenrieder, C. Vogt, H. Faber, L. Büthe, G. Cantarella, F. Bottacchi, T.D. Anthopoulos, G. Tröster, Metal oxide semiconductor thin-film transistors for flexible electronics, *Appl. Phys. Rev.* 3 (2016) 021303, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4953034>.
- [73] R.B. Rashid, W. Du, S. Griggs, I.P. Maria, I. McCulloch, J. Rivnay, Ambipolar inverters based on cofacial vertical organic electrochemical transistor pairs for biosignal amplification, *Sci. Adv.* 7 (2021) eabh1055.
- [74] C. Jiang, H.W. Choi, X. Cheng, H. Ma, D. Hasko, A. Nathan, Printed subthreshold organic transistors operating at high gain and ultralow power, *Science* 363 (2019) 719–723.
- [75] T.-C. Huang, K. Fukuda, C.-M. Lo, Y.-H. Yeh, T. Sekitani, T. Someya, K.-T. Cheng, Pseudo-CMOS: A novel design style for flexible electronics, 2010 Design, Automation & Test in Europe Conference & Exhibition (DATE 2010), IEEE, 2010, pp. 154–159.
- [76] S. Wang, J. Xu, W. Wang, G.-J.N. Wang, R. Rastak, F. Molina-Lopez, J.W. Chung, S. Niu, V.R. Feig, J. Lopez, Skin electronics from scalable fabrication of an intrinsically stretchable transistor array, *Nature* 555 (2018) 83–88.
- [77] K. Ishida, R. Shabanpour, B.K. Boroujeni, T. Meister, C. Carta, F. Ellinger, L. Petti, N.S. Münzenrieder, G.A. Salvatore, G. Tröster, 22.5 dB open-loop gain, 31 kHz GSW pseudo-CMOS based operational amplifier with a-IGZO TFTs on a flexible film, 2014 IEEE Asian Solid-State Circuits Conference (A-SSCC), IEEE, 2014, pp. 313–316.
- [78] M. Sugiyama, T. Uemura, M. Kondo, M. Akiyama, N. Namba, S. Yoshimoto, Y. Noda, T. Araki, T. Sekitani, An ultraflexible organic differential amplifier for recording electrocardiograms, *Nat. Electron.* 2 (2019) 351–360.
- [79] R. Shi, X. Liu, T. Lei, L. Lu, Z. Xia, M. Wong, An integrated analog front-end system on flexible substrate for the acquisition of bio-potential signals, *Adv. Sci.* 10 (2023) 2207683.
- [80] R. Shiwaku, H. Matsui, K. Nagamine, M. Uematsu, T. Mano, Y. Maruyama, A. Nomura, K. Tsuchiya, K. Hayasaka, Y. Takeda, A printed organic amplification system for wearable potentiometric electrochemical sensors, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (2018) 3922.
- [81] L. Xiang, Y. Wang, F. Xia, F. Liu, D. He, G. Long, X. Zeng, X. Liang, C. Jin, Y. Wang, An epidermal electronic system for physiological information acquisition, processing, and storage with an integrated flash memory array, *Sci. Adv.* 8 (2022) eabp8075.
- [82] M. Fattori, S. Cardarelli, J. Fijn, P. Harpe, M. Charbonneau, D. Locatelli, S. Lombard, C. Laugier, L. Tournon, S. Jacob, A printed proximity-sensing surface based on organic pyroelectric sensors and organic thin-film transistor electronics, *Nat. Electron.* 5 (2022) 289–299.
- [83] D.K. Polyushkin, S. Wächter, L. Mennel, M. Paur, M. Paliy, G. Iannaccone, G. Fiori, D. Neumaier, B. Canto, T. Mueller, Analogue two-dimensional semiconductor electronics, *Nat. Electron.* 3 (2020) 486–491.
- [84] J. Xiao, Z. Kang, B. Liu, X. Zhang, J. Du, K. Chen, H. Yu, Q. Liao, Z. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Record-high saturation current in end-bond contacted monolayer MoS₂ transistors, *Nano Res.* 15 (2022) 475–481.
- [85] J. Chang, X. Zhang, T. Ge, J. Zhou, Fully printed electronics on flexible substrates, high gain amplifiers and DAC, *Org. Electron.* 15 (2014) 701–710.
- [86] S. Elsaegh, C. Veit, U. Zschieschang, M. Amayreh, F. Letzkus, H. Sailer, M. Jurisch, J.N. Burghartz, U. Würfel, H. Klauk, Low-power organic light sensor array based on active-matrix common-gate transimpedance amplifier on foil for imaging applications, *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits* 55 (2020) 2553–2566.
- [87] M. Seifaei, D. De Dorigo, D.I. Fleig, M. Kuhl, U. Zschieschang, H. Klauk, Y. Manoli, Stable, self-biased and high-gain organic amplifiers with reduced parameter variation effect, 2018 IEEE Asian Solid-State Circuits Conference (A-SSCC), IEEE, 2018, pp. 119–122.
- [88] C. Zysset, N. Münzenrieder, L. Petti, L. Büthe, G.A. Salvatore, G. Tröster, IGZO TFT-based all-enhancement operational amplifier bent to a radius of 5 mm, *IEEE Electron Device Lett.* 34 (2013) 1394–1396.
- [89] C. Garripoli, J.-L.P. van der Steen, F. Torricelli, M. Ghittoelli, G.H. Gelinck, A.H. Van Roermund, E. Cantatore, Analogue frontend amplifiers for bio-potential measurements manufactured with a-IGZO TFTs on flexible substrate, *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel.* 7 (2016) 60–70.
- [90] Z.-J. Chen, W.-X. Xu, J.-D. Wu, L. Zhou, W.-J. Wu, J.-H. Zou, M. Xu, L. Wang, Y.-R. Liu, J.-B. Peng, A new high-gain operational amplifier using transconductance-enhancement topology integrated with metal oxide TFTs, *IEEE J. Electron Devices Soc.* 7 (2019) 111–117, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JEDS.2018.2883585>.

- [91] A. Noda, H. Shinoda, Inter-IC for Wearables (I 2 We), Power and data transfer over double-sided conductive textile, *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Circuits Syst.* 13 (2018) 80–90.
- [92] P. Corbhisley, E. Rodriguez-Villegas, A nanopower bandpass filter for detection of an acoustic signal in a wearable breathing detector, *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Circuits Syst.* 1 (2007) 163–171.
- [93] Z. Liu, Y. Tan, H. Li, H. Jiang, J. Liu, H. Liao, A 0.5-V 3.69-nW complementary source-follower-C based low-pass filter for wearable biomedical applications, *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I Regul. Pap.* 67 (2020) 4370–4381.
- [94] A. Noda, H. Shinoda, Simplex inter-IC for wearables and its applications, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 69654–69662.
- [95] R. Worsley, L. Pimpolari, D. McManus, N. Ge, R. Ionescu, J.A. Wittkopf, A. Alieva, G. Basso, M. Macucci, G. Iannaccone, All-2D material inkjet-printed capacitors: toward fully printed integrated circuits, *ACS Nano* 13 (2018) 54–60.
- [96] F. Alkhalil, T. Smith, H. Su, F. Rodriguez, A. Reardon, B. Cobb, Flexible SAR ADC with resistive DAC for conformable on-body sensing applications, 2022 *IEEE Biomedical Circuits and Systems Conference (BioCAS)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 110–114.
- [97] N. Papadopoulos, F. De Roose, Y.-C. Lai, J.-L. van der Steen, M. Ameys, W. Dehaene, J. Genoe, K. Myny, Flexible self-biased 66.7 nJ/cs 6bit 26S/s successive-approximation C-2C ADC with offset cancellation using unipolar metal-oxide TFTs, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE Custom Integrated Circuits Conference (CICC)*, Austin, TX, USA, 2017, pp. 1–4 <doi:10.1109/CICC.2017.7993671>.
- [98] N.P. Papadopoulos, F. De Roose, J.-L.P. van der Steen, E.C. Smits, M. Ameys, W. Dehaene, J. Genoe, K. Myny, Toward temperature tracking with unipolar metal-oxide thin-film SAR C-2C ADC on plastic, *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits* 53 (2018) 2263–2272.
- [99] H. Marien, M. Steyaert, N. van Aarle, P. Heremans, An analog organic first-order CT $\Delta\Sigma$ ADC on a flexible plastic substrate with 26.5 dB precision, 2010 *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference-(ISSCC)*, IEEE, 2010, pp. 136–137.
- [100] H. Marien, M.S. Steyaert, E. van Venendaal, P. Heremans, A Fully Integrated $\Delta\Sigma$ ADC in organic thin-film transistor technology on flexible plastic foil, *IEEE J. Solid-State Circuits* 46 (2010) 276–284.
- [101] N. Wadhwa, P. Bahubalindruni, A. Correia, J. Goes, S. Deb, P. Barquinha, Mostly passive $\Delta\Sigma$ ADC with a-IGZO TFTs for flexible electronics, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, Austin, TX, USA, 2021, pp. 1–6 <doi:10.1109/CICC.2017.7993671>.
- [102] M. Zulqarnain, S. Stanzione, G. Rathinavel, S. Smout, M. Willegems, K. Myny, E. Cantatore, A flexible ECG patch compatible with NFC RF communication, *npj Flex. Electron.* 4 (2020) 13, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41528-020-0077-x>.
- [103] W. Sun, Q. Zhao, F. Qiao, Y. Liu, H. Yang, X. Guo, L. Zhou, L. Wang, An 8b 0.8 kS/s configurable VCO-based ADC using oxide TFTs with Inkjet printing interconnection, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, Baltimore, MD, USA, 2017, pp. 1–4 <doi:10.1109/ISCAS.2017.8050682>.
- [104] D. Raiteri, P. van Lieshout, A. van Roermund, E. Cantatore, An organic VCO-based ADC for quasi-static signals achieving 1LSB INL at 6b resolution, 2013 *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference Digest of Technical Papers*, IEEE, 2013, pp. 108–109.
- [105] S. Abdinia, M. Benwadih, R. Coppard, S. Jacob, G. Maiellaro, G. Palmisano, M. Rizzo, A. Scuderi, F. Tramontana, A. van Roermund, A 4b ADC manufactured in a fully-printed organic complementary technology including resistors, 2013 *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference Digest of Technical Papers*, IEEE, 2013, pp. 106–107.
- [106] A. Dey, D.R. Allee, Amorphous silicon 5 bit flash analog to digital converter, *Proceedings of the IEEE 2012 Custom Integrated Circuits Conference*, IEEE, 2012, pp. 1–4.
- [107] A. Jamshidi-Roudbari, P.-C. Kuo, M.K. Hatalis, A flash analog to digital converter on stainless steel foil substrate, *Solid-State Electron.* 54 (2010) 410–416.
- [108] S. Nasiri, M.R. Khosravani, Progress and challenges in fabrication of wearable sensors for health monitoring, *Sens. Actuators A Phys.* 312 (2020) 112105, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2020.112105>.
- [109] L. Lombardo, S. Corbellini, M. Parvis, A. Elsayed, E. Angelini, S. Grassini, Wireless sensor network for distributed environmental monitoring, *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.* 67 (2017) 1214–1222.
- [110] B. Jr, U. Reddy, C. Hassan, D. Seymour, T. Angus, K. Isbell, W. White, L. Weir, A. Yeh, R. Vincent, Bashir, Point-of-care sensors for the management of sepsis, *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* 2 (2018) 640–648.
- [111] K. Xu, Y. Lu, K. Takei, Flexible hybrid sensor systems with feedback functions, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 31 (2021) 2007436.
- [112] Z. Kappassov, J.-A. Corrales, V. Perdereau, Tactile sensing in dexterous robot hands, *Robot. Auton. Syst.* 74 (2015) 195–220.
- [113] R.S. Dahiya, M. Valle, *Robotic Tactile Sensing: Technologies and System*, Springer, 2013 Vol. 1.
- [114] Y. Wu, Y. Liu, Y. Zhou, Q. Man, C. Hu, W. Asghar, F. Li, Z. Yu, J. Shang, G. Liu, A skin-inspired tactile sensor for smart prosthetics, *Sci. Robot.* 3 (2018) eaat0429.
- [115] G. Ogunniye, N. Kokciyan, A survey on understanding and representing privacy requirements in the Internet-of-Things, *J. Artif. Intell.* 76 (2023) 163–192.
- [116] Y. Song, J. Min, Y. Yu, H. Wang, Y. Yang, H. Zhang, W. Gao, Wireless battery-free wearable sweat sensor powered by human motion, *Sci. Adv.* 6 (2020) eaay9842.
- [117] J.-Y. Yoo, S. Oh, W. Shalish, W.-Y. Maeng, E. Cerier, E. Jeanne, M.-K. Chung, S. Lv, Y. Wu, S. Yoo, Wireless broadband acousto-mechanical sensing system for continuous physiological monitoring, *Nat. Med.* 29 (2023) 3137–3148.
- [118] P. Escobedo, M. Bhattacharjee, F. Nikbakhtnasrabadi, R. Dahiya, Smart bandage with wireless strain and temperature sensors and batteryless NFC tag, *IEEE Internet Things J.* 8 (2020) 5093–5100.
- [119] H. Ozaki, T. Kawamura, H. Wakana, T. Yamazoe, H. Uchiyama, 20- μ W operation of an a-IGZO TFT-based RFID chip using purely NMOS “active” load logic gates with ultra-low-consumption power, 2011 *Symposium on VLSI Circuits-Digest of Technical Papers*, IEEE, 2011, pp. 54–55.
- [120] K. Myny, S. Steudel, 16.6 flexible thin-film NFC transponder chip exhibiting data rates compatible to ISO NFC standards using self-aligned metal-oxide TFTs, 2016 *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, IEEE, 2016, pp. 298–299.
- [121] K. Myny, B. Cobb, J.-L. van der Steen, A.K. Tripathi, J. Genoe, G. Gelinck, P. Heremans, 16.3 Flexible thin-film NFC tags powered by commercial USB reader device at 13.56 MHz, 2015 *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference-(ISSCC) Digest of Technical Papers*, IEEE, 2015, pp. 1–3.
- [122] L. Zhang, H. Ji, H. Huang, N. Yi, X. Shi, S. Xie, Y. Li, Z. Ye, P. Feng, T. Lin, Wearable circuits sintered at room temperature directly on the skin surface for health monitoring, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 12 (2020) 45504–45515.
- [123] S. Gandla, S. Kang, J. Kim, Y. Yu, J. Kim, H. Lim, H.-J. Kwon, S.-M. Park, S. Kim, Flex-to-stretch hybrid electronics—bonding-free robust interface for wearable wireless physiological monitoring, *IEEE Internet Things J.* 11 (2024) 15656–15666, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2024.3350022>.
- [124] H. Kandárová, P. Pöbösi, The “Big Three” in biocompatibility testing of medical devices: implementation of alternatives to animal experimentation—are we there yet? *Front. Toxicol.* 5 (2024) 1337468.
- [125] P. Bhushan, V. Kamat, I. Abrol, A. Kaushik, S. Bhansali, Bio-acceptability of wearable sensors: a mechanistic study towards evaluating ionic leaching induced cellular inflammation, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (2022) 10782.
- [126] Q. Huang, Z. Zheng, Pathway to developing permeable electronics, *ACS Nano* 16 (2022) 15537–15544.
- [127] P. Pursula, K. Kiri, C. Mc Caffrey, H. Sandberg, J. Vartiainen, J. Flak, P. Lahtinen, Nanocellulose–polyurethane substrate material with tunable mechanical properties for wearable electronics, *Flex. Print. Electron.* 3 (2018) 045002.
- [128] M. Mariello, K. Kim, K. Wu, S.P. Lacour, Y. Leterrier, Recent advances in encapsulation of flexible bioelectronic implants: materials, technologies, and characterization methods, *Adv. Mater.* 34 (2022) 2201129.
- [129] C. Randell, H.L. Muller, The well mannered wearable computer, *Pers. Ubiquitous Comput.* 6 (2002) 31–36.
- [130] S. Mann, Smart clothing: The shift to wearable computing, *Commun. ACM* 39 (1996) 23–24.
- [131] J. Biggs, J. Myers, J. Kufel, E. Ozer, S. Craske, A. Sou, C. Ramsdale, K. Williamson, R. Price, S. White, A natively flexible 32-bit arm microprocessor, *Nature* 595 (2021) 532–536.
- [132] A. Ometov, V. Shubina, L. Klus, J. Skibińska, S. Saafi, P. Pascacio, L. Flueraoru, D.Q. Gaibor, N. Chukhno, O. Chukhno, A survey on wearable technology: History, state-of-the-art and current challenges, *Comput. Netw.* 193 (2021) 108074.
- [133] H.C. Ates, P.Q. Nguyen, L. Gonzalez-Macia, E. Morales-Narváez, F. Güder, J.J. Collins, C. Dincer, End-to-end design of wearable sensors, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* 7 (2022) 887–907.
- [134] E. Ozer, J. Kufel, J. Biggs, A. Rana, F.J. Rodríguez, T. Lee-Clark, A. Sou, C. Ramsdale, S. White, S.K. Garlapati, P. Valliappan, A. Rahmanudin, V. Komanduri, G.S. Saez, S. Gollu, G. Brown, P. Dudek, K.C. Persaud, M.L. Turner, S. Murray, S. Bates, R. Treloar, B. Newby, J. Ford, Malodour classification with low-cost flexible electronics, *Nat. Commun.* 14 (2023) 777, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-36104-z>.
- [135] E. Ozer, J. Kufel, J. Myers, J. Biggs, G. Brown, A. Rana, A. Sou, C. Ramsdale, S. White, A hardware machine learning processing engine fabricated with submicron metal-oxide thin-film transistors on a flexible substrate, *Nat. Electron.* 3 (2020) 419–425.
- [136] F. Cleary, W. Srisa-an, B. Gil, J. Kesavan, T. Engel, D.C. Henshall, S. Balasubramanian, Wearable fabric μ brain enabling on-garment edge-based sensor data processing, *IEEE Sens. J.* 22 (2022) 20839–20854.
- [137] Y. Wang, H. Tang, Y. Xie, X. Chen, S. Ma, Z. Sun, Q. Sun, L. Chen, H. Zhu, J. Wan, An in-memory computing architecture based on two-dimensional semiconductors for multiply-accumulate operations, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 3347.
- [138] S. Ma, T. Wu, X. Chen, Y. Wang, H. Tang, Y. Yao, Y. Wang, Z. Zhu, J. Deng, J. Wan, An artificial neural network chip based on two-dimensional semiconductor, *Sci. Bull.* 67 (2022) 270–277.
- [139] W. Taube Navaraj, C. García Núñez, D. Shakthivel, V. Vinciguerra, F. Labeau, D.H. Gregory, R. Dahiya, Nanowire FET based neural element for robotic tactile sensing skin, *Front. Neurosci.* 11 (2017) 281654.
- [140] F. Liu, S. Deswal, A. Christou, M. Shojaei Baghini, R. Chirila, D. Shakthivel, M. Chakraborty, R. Dahiya, Printed synaptic transistor-based electronic skin for robots to feel and learn, *Sci. Robot.* 7 (2022) eabl7286.
- [141] M.J.M. Hosseini, Y. Yang, A.J. Prendergast, E. Donati, M. Faezipour, G. Indiveri, R.A. Nawrocki, An organic synaptic circuit: toward flexible and biocompatible organic neuromorphic processing, *Neuromorphic Comput. Eng.* 2 (2022) 034009.
- [142] P.C. Harikesh, C.-Y. Yang, D. Tu, J.Y. Gerasimov, A.M. Dar, A. Armada-Moreira, M. Masetti, R. Kroon, D. Bliman, R. Olsson, Organic electrochemical neurons and synapses with ion mediated spiking, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 901.
- [143] T. Fu, X. Liu, S. Fu, T. Woodard, H. Gao, D.R. Lovley, J. Yao, Self-sustained green neuromorphic interfaces, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 3351.
- [144] W. Wang, Y. Jiang, D. Zhong, Z. Zhang, S. Choudhury, J.-C. Lai, H. Gong, S. Niu, X. Yan, Y. Zheng, Neuromorphic sensorimotor loop embodied by monolithically integrated, low-voltage, soft e-skin, *Science* 380 (2023) 735–742.
- [145] Q. Lai, L. Zhang, Z. Li, W.F. Stickle, R.S. Williams, Y. Chen, Ionic/electronic hybrid materials integrated in a synaptic transistor with signal processing and learning functions, *Adv. Mater.* 22 (2010) 2448–2453.
- [146] B.C.-K. Tee, A. Chortos, A. Berndt, A.K. Nguyen, A. Tom, A. McGuire, Z.C. Lin, K. Tien, W.-G. Bae, H. Wang, A skin-inspired organic digital mechanoreceptor, *Science* 350 (2015) 313–316.
- [147] Y. Lin, M. Bariya, A. Javey, Wearable biosensors for body computing, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 31 (2021) 2008087.
- [148] Y. Luo, M.R. Abidian, J.-H. Ahn, D. Akinwande, A.M. Andrews, M. Antonietti, Z. Bao, M. Berggren, C.A. Berkey, C.J. Bettinger, Technology roadmap for flexible sensors, *ACS Nano* 17 (2023) 5211–5295.